

ggret: An R package for visualising and manipulating tree-based phylogenetic networks

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1 Summary

The evolutionary relationships of biological entities are most often represented with phylogenetic trees. Phylogenetic trees consist of branches (or edges) representing direct lines of descents or genetic flow from ancestor to offspring (i.e. lineages), and nodes representing evolutionary "splits" through which a parental lineage gives rise to multiple child lineages. This vertical model of evolution has provided immense insights into the evolutionary history and processes underlying observed biological diversity. However, it fails to account for "horizontal" modes of evolution, whereby genetic material can be exchanged between contemporaneous organisms through a variety of mechanism across the tree of life (Arnold et al. (2022); Keeling (2024); Pérez-Losada et al. (2015)). In recent years, advances in sequencing technologies and computational methods have made it increasingly possible to integrate horizontal evolutionary events into reticulated phylogenetic trees (or phylogenetic networks; (Huson and Bryant (2006))). While phylogenetic networks have the potential to provide more comprehensive and accurate evolutionary pictures for many biological groups, the development of specific tools is required for their manipulation and visualisation.

2 Statement of Need

ggret is an R package for the visualisation of tree-based phylogenetic networks (i.e. phylogenetic trees with additional horizontal edges). The R language is commonly used for phylogenetic analysis and visualisation with packages such as ape and ggtree providing important functionalities for phylogenetic research (Paradis and Schliep (2019); Yu et al. (2017)). ggret builds up on these functionalities by extending ggtree with methods for handling tree-based phylogenetic networks while maintaining compatibility between the packages. Additionally, it enables the user to parse data formats for phylogenetic networks (extended Newick and NEXUS) and handle associated metadata via treedata objects.

3 Usage

ggret is available on GitHub and can be installed by using remotes' `install_github` function.

```
if (!requireNamespace("remotes", quietly=TRUE))
  install.packages("remotes")
remotes::install_github("grdspcht/ggret", dependencies = TRUE, build_vignettes = TRUE)
```

ggret provides functions for reading extended Newick and (*BEAST2*) NEXUS format (Cardona et al. (2008)). This allows the user to visualise phylogenetic networks inferred from various programs. Here we parsed a (summary) phylogenetic network simulated with the *BEAST2* package *Bacter* (Vaughan et al. (2017)) containing various node metadata, using the `read_beast_retnet` function. Note that the resulting `retnet` `treedata` object has been directly included in the package for the sake of reproducibility.

```
retfile <- system.file("extdata", "retnet.nexus", package = "ggret", mustWork =
  TRUE)
retnet <- ggret::read_beast_retnet(retfile)
```

ggret is the central function of this package. In a simple call without additional arguments it plots rudimentary tree-based network without labelling. Reticulated edges are drawn as black dashed lines by default, but ggret contains various arguments to change their configuration (e.g. colour, linetype, etc.) (Figure 1).

```
library(ggret)

#simple network
p1 <- ggret::ggret(retnet)
#reticulation edges displayed as red dotted lines, in a "snake" shape
p2 <- ggret::ggret(retnet,retcol = "red",retlinetype = 3)
#reticulation edges displayed as blue solid lines, in a straight shape and with
  arrow heads
p3 <- ggret::ggret(retnet,retcol = "blue",retlinetype = 1,arrows = T,rettype ="
  straight")
```


Figure 1. Three simple tree-based networks plotted with ggret

Annotations can be added using ggtree functions, such as geom_tiplab, geom_nodelab and geom_range. In addition, a time axis can be added as using the theme_tree2 theme (Figure 2).

```
# Get the tMRCA of the tree and define time points to display in the time axis in
  years BP
tmrca <- phytools::nodeHeights(retnet@phylo) %>% max
xticks_BP=c(20000,15000,10000,5000,0)

# Add tip and node labels (we expand the x axis limits so that tip labels still fit
  in
p1 <- p1 +
  ggtree::geom_tiplab() +
  ggtree::geom_nodelab(aes(label=round(posterior,2)),vjust=-0.25,hjust=1.3,size=3)
  +
  ggplot2::expand_limits(x=22000)

# Adding a time axis and node bars indicating node heights' 95% highest posterior
  density interval
p1 <- p1 +
  ggtree::theme_tree2() +
  ggtree::geom_range(aes(range="height_95_HPD"), color="grey50", alpha=.6, size
    =1.5) +
```

```
ggtree::scale_x_continuous(breaks = tmrca - xticks_BP, labels=xticks_BP) +
ggplot2::xlab("Years_before_present")
```


Figure 2. Annotated phylogenetic network.

The `group_clade` function can be used to define clades within a network and color them accordingly. `group_clade` assigns clade information to all nodes descending from the MRCA of tips specified in the `nodes` argument (Figure 3).

```
# Define clades using the group_clade function
retnet %>%
  ggret::group_clade(nodes = c("taxon_10", "taxon_20"), cladename = "A",
    addtotreedata = T) %>%
  ggret::group_clade(nodes = c("taxon_11", "taxon_15"), cladename = "B",
    addtotreedata = T) %>%
  ggret::group_clade(nodes = c("taxon_1", "taxon_16"), cladename = "C",
    addtotreedata = T) ->
  rernet_clade

# Plot network with colored clades
ggret::ggret(retnet_clade, aes(color=clade))
```


Figure 3. Phylogenetic network with edge colors based on clade information.

Code availability

For additional information, refer to ggret's internal documentation or to <https://github.com/grdspcht/ggret> which also gives users the opportunity to open issues, pull requests or report bugs.

References

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